

PROCESSING, PROPERTIES AND APPLICATIONS OF P/M MAGNESIUM-SiC_p-COMPOSITES

J. Schröder, K.U. Kainer*

Zentrum für Funktionswerkstoffe g. GmbH, Sachsenweg 1c,
D-3392 Clausthal-Zellerfeld (F.R.G.)

*Institut für Werkstoffkunde und Werkstofftechnik,
Technische Universität Clausthal, Agricolastr. 6,
D-3392 Clausthal-Zellerfeld (F.R.G.)

ABSTRACT

Particle reinforced magnesium alloys are interesting materials for technological applications because they exhibit higher stiffness, smaller thermal expansion and a higher wear resistance than conventional magnesium alloys. There is only a little increase in density due to the reinforcement. Magnesium and SiC can react and hence the manufacture conditions have a large influence on the structure and properties of composites. In the present work composites were produced with the magnesium alloy QE22 using various powder metallurgical techniques. The influence of the production method on the microstructure and the mechanical properties was investigated.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the last few years the interest in high strength materials with low specific weight has continuously increased. Magnesium based materials are potential construction materials, but the low stiffness, strength and corrosion resistance limited their applications in automotive and aircraft industry. In the past the properties of commercial magnesium alloys were improved by the addition of alloying elements such as silver, rare earth, zirconium and thorium. However, these alloying developments led to an improvement of mechanical properties at room and elevated temperature but for sufficient stiffness and wear resistance the addition of hard and stiff reinforcements is required.

Different routes are available for the production of magnesium composites, eg the introduction of particles in melts, spray compaction (3-5), infiltration of preforms and powder metallurgical methods (1,2). Due to the high reactivity of molten magnesium, chemical reactions between the matrix alloy and the reinforcement are possible and so not all production methods led to composites with good mechanical properties. Thus, powder metallurgical and spray deposition methods are preferred to produce magnesium matrix composites.

The spray deposition, known as the Osprey process, offers a combination of the advantages of powder metallurgical rapid solidification technologies (RSP) with those of conventional production methods (3,4). However, due to the porosity in the sprayed preforms a further transformation by extrusion or forging is necessary.

2. PRODUCTION OF COMPOSITES

The high temperature magnesium alloy QE22 with the alloying elements rare earth and silver was used as matrix alloy (Tab. 1). The reinforcements were silicon carbide particles with a mean diameter of approximately 8-12 μ m. These reinforcements are characterized by a high hardness of about 9.7 Mohs hardness, high stiffness (400 GPa) and a low coefficient of thermal expansion ($4.7 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$).

	Chemical Composition in %						
	Ag	RE	Zr	Mn	Si	Cu	Fe
QE22	2.5	2.0	0.6	0.03	0.01	0.01	0.003

RE= Rare Earth

Table I: Chemical Composition of the Matrix Alloy (Balance Mg)

The different production techniques of composites are schematically shown in Fig. 1 and Fig. 1. Four different processes were used to consolidate the mixtures of powders and particles: spray forming of composite preforms and subsequent deformation by extrusion, extrusion of overspray from the Osprey process, extrusion of powder mixtures of particles and gas atomized powders and powder forging of powder mixtures of particles and gas atomized powders.

Fig. 1: Flow chart of composite production

a) spray forming and extrusion of overspray

b) consolidation of powder/particle mixtures by extrusion or forging

The principle of spray compaction technology is shown in the Fig. 2. Starting by melting the alloys in a vacuum induction furnace the melt stream will be disintegrated to fine matrix powders in a gas atomization unit. A special particle injector enables the addition of particles into the atomizing chamber. The mixture of matrix droplets (semisolid powder) and particles is consolidated on a rotating substrate. Using the spray compaction technology the production of semifinished preforms Fig. 3 and near net shape tubes is possible.

Fig. 2: Principles of spray compaction of particle reinforced alloys /6/

Fig. 3: Composite preforms of magnesium alloy QE22 reinforced with SiC_p

To investigate the influence of the production method two other consolidation technologies were used to prepare the composite materials. These P/M routes are schematically shown in Fig. 1b. Rapidly solidified QE22 powder were produced by inert gas atomization. During gas atomization of these powder, a low content of oxygen, less than 2 wt.%, was added to the argon in order to passivate the powder particles. The mean diameter of the matrix powder was fixed at 80 μm using a classification by sieving. Matrix powder and hard particles were mixed in a special mixing/milling process. Consolidation of these mixtures takes place in one case by capsulation and hot extrusion at 380 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. The other compacting method was a new developed powder forging technology.

Fig. 4: Microstructure of magnesium powder (alloy: QE22)

The microstructure of the rapidly solidified magnesium powder is given in Fig. 4. The gas atomized powder showed a spherical shape with a fine cellular microstructure. Similar microstructures are obtained for the overspray from the spray forming.

The Mg-Ag-Nd system offers the possibility of a precipitation hardening. In the case of lower silver content, less than 2%, the preferred intermetallic phase is Mg_{12}Nd , whereas a higher amount of silver leads to the more complex phase $\text{Mg}_{12}\text{Nd}_2\text{Ag}$. Thus, all composite materials were examined in the two different conditions: a) as processed, without subsequent treatment, b) heat treated, T6 condition(8h solution treatment at 798 K, 8h precipitation hardening at 477 K).

3. MICROSTRUCTURES OF COMPOSITES

Fig. 5 shows the microstructures of particle reinforced magnesium composites depending on the production technique. A comparison of the microstructures of the extruded spray formed composite and of the extruded overspray powder showed no significant difference in particle distribution and structure. Composites produced by extrusion of

powder/particle mixtures (P/M) in Fig. 5a are characterized by an excellent distribution of particles. This is a result of optimized mixing techniques and the choice of a suitable powder/particle size relationship (5:1). The Osprey composite materials (Fig. 5b) showed in the as sprayed condition an insufficient particle distribution. The particles are clustered along the surface of consolidated matrix powder and a high amount of

Fig. 5: Microstructures of Mg-SiC-composites depending on the production technology
a) extruded powder/particle mixtures b) spray formed
c) spray formed and extruded

pores and unreinforced areas are visible. However, the conditions during the spray forming were not optimized for the examined magnesium alloy. A further working of the sprayed composites by extrusion at 380°C led to an improvement of the particle distribution (Fig. 5c). During the extrusion clusters were deagglomerated and the amount of pores was reduced from 20% to less than 0.5 %.

4. MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

The mechanical properties of composites with the same composition (QE22 + 15% SiC) are summarized in Fig. 6. The unreinforced alloy shows in the extruded condition a hardness of about 85 HV10. During the heat treatment first the work hardening effect due to the extrusion will be removed. As a result the hardness is decreasing. During the subsequent aging an increase of hardness occurs. Both effects summarized led to a hardness in the T6 condition that is close to those of the extruded materials. The addition of the stiff SiC particles led to an improvement of Young's modulus. Unreinforced magnesium alloys are characterized by a low E-modulus of about 45 GPa. The elastic moduli are improved significantly by the addition of 15 Vol.% particle

reinforcement up to 70 GPa. This gives an improvement of about 55 % and leads to a stiffness that is close to that of conventional aluminium alloys. Differences in the stiffness depending on the production processes are a result of different bonding and

Fig. 6: Mechanical properties of magnesium-SiCp-composites depending on the production technique (alloy QE22)

load transfer conditions between matrix and reinforcement. The results of tensile test demonstrate that the 0.2 proof stress is dependent on the processing method used. A high proof stress of about 290 MPa was obtained for the Osprey material in the extruded condition. However, the elongation to fracture of this material was less than 1%. The extruded PM mixtures and powder forged materials showed a lower proof stress close to the matrix values, whereas a higher elongation to fracture up to 4% was obtained. The particle reinforcement led to an improvement of strength of about 20 %. Markable is that all materials in the extruded and heat treated condition reached nearly the same strength of about 300 MPa. Even the overspray material is a suitable prematerial for composite production.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Light metal matrix composites with discontinuous reinforcements offer more isotropic properties and the reinforcements and composite production is compared with continuously reinforced materials not so expensive. Thus they are interesting for the mass production in different industries, especially for constructions where good mechanical properties and also a low density is required.

Spray forming and hot pressing and extrusion of particle powder mixtures are suitable technologies to produce magnesium base composites. The results showed, that if a sufficient distribution of particles is guaranteed, an improvement of mechanical properties compared with those of unreinforced alloys is obtained. Markable is that, if the final processing step is done by extrusion, all materials showed comparable mechanical properties. This investigation has shown, that overspray powder, normally a waste product of spray compaction, can be used as prematerial for the composite production.

6. REFERENCES

1. J. Schröder, K.U. Kainer, B. Mordike, "Powder Metallurgically Produced Particle Reinforced Magnesium Alloys", Proceedings PM '90, London, 1990, 304-309.
2. J. Schröder, K.U. Kainer, "Correlation between Structure and Mechanical Properties of SiC Particle Reinforced Magnesium Alloys, Proceedings Euromat '91, The Institute of Materials, 1991, Vol.2, 81-91.
3. P. Mathur, D. Apelian, A. Lawley, "Analysis of the Spray Deposition Process", Acta Metallurgica, 37 (2), 1989, 429-443.
4. A.R.E. Singer, S. Ozbek, "Metal Matrix Composites Produced by Spray Codeposition", Powder Metallurgy, 28, 1985, 72-78.
5. T.J. Warner et al., "Microstructure and Properties of Spray Deposited Al Alloy/SiC Composites", in Interfaces in Polymer, Ceramic and MMC, ed. Hatsu Ishida, Elsevier, 1988, 537-551.
6. Information sheet, Osprey Metals Ltd., Neath, West Glam, UK.